

Project acronym: BYTE
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Deliverable D9.3: BYTE Showcase video

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1 THE BYTE SHOWCASE VIDEO

As part of the final dissemination work for BYTE, the project produced a Showcase video for the project and the European Commission to use to publicise the project, the BYTE Big Data Community and the work undertaken. At the close of the project, the BYTE consortium produced a 3 minute video, using icon-based animation techniques currently popular in this genre. The video was produced by KIFU, in collaboration with CNR, TRI and UIBK.

The video outlines the purpose of the BYTE project, describing the context, the project's main objectives and the reason the project was funded.

The video also demonstrates how European experts were invited to participate in project activities.

The video also highlights European Commission funding in supporting the project and driving the research.

The video also highlights the BYTE case studies and the roadmap, and points viewers to where they can find more information.

The video ends by describing how interested individuals can get involved in the BYTE Big Data Community and the further activities after the close of the project.

1.1 SCRIPT

The following is the script used in the video to showcase the BYTE project and invite people to join the community.

BYTE Showcase video Script

For the last few years, policy makers, news outlets and experts across different fields have been talking about the promises and perils of “big data”. What they mean is the collection and processing of vast data sets that might be very diverse and might be changing in real time.

The European Commission asked legal experts, academics, political scientists, technology experts and privacy experts to come together for two reasons. First, to help create policies that would enable the benefits of big data, and second to ensure that big data practices were responsible. The BYTE project was the result of the Commission’s call to action. The project is made up of 11 partners from 10 countries and has run for three years.

BYTE has used “real world” evidence to identify opportunities and challenges in big data; challenges like new business models or privacy concerns. The project used seven case studies in different sectors (INSERT IMAGE) to identify real achievements and concerns. BYTE then identified potential solutions to problems that could come about in the future if actors do not take a responsible approach.

The outcome of the project is a research roadmap and a policy roadmap for big data in Europe. The research roadmap focuses on what we need to be able to do and what questions we need to answer to support responsible big data practices. The policy roadmap focuses on what governments and large institutions need to do to create an appropriate legal and policy space for responsible European innovation. This includes changes to EU-US data relations, to Intellectual Property Rights and privacy principles, as well as support for changing industries.

BYTE is also organising a community of legal experts, social scientists and civil society organisations, to feed citizens’ concerns directly to industry. The BYTE Big Data Community

will be embedded within the Big Data Value Association, a network of industry and academic practitioners driving data innovations, in cooperation with the European Commission.

BYTE is inviting interested organisations to participate in the Community. Through BYTE they can speak directly to industry during Big Data Value networking events. Community members can also participate directly in setting up the European research priorities and get involved in designing the European research work programme.

To find out more or to join the BYTE Big Data Community, please visit our website. (Image) Click on Community to go directly to the community portal.

Thanks for listening, and we hope to welcome you as a member soon!

1.2 VIDEO POSTING

The video has been posted to a BYTE YouTube channel and can be accessed here: https://youtu.be/_8pP4UmJrL0 or directly on the BYTE website.